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New Material Removal Tools and Processes to Safely Expedite Maintenance on Composite Structures

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Material Removal Maintenance Issues

- Significant time required to remove materials from composite aerospace structures to facilitate maintenance (sealants, coatings, gap fillers, adhesives)
- Specified nonmetallic scraper blades and other tools are inefficient
- Alternative tools and methods used to expedite removal often cause damage
- Repetitive motion injuries common for aircraft maintainers removing materials

Composite Damage

Inefficient Nonmetallic Tools

Potential for Damage

Torlon® Scraper Blades (TSBs)

- TSBs developed in-house at AFRL
- Fabricated from Torlon® 5030; 5 widths
- More rigid than other nonmetallic scrapers; chemical resistant and usable to 260°C
- Hold edges longer and easy to sharpen
- Used with handles and pneumatic tool
- Readily machinable to specialized shapes

TSB Kit

Torlon Gap Blades (TGBs)

- Unique Torlon 5030 TGBs designed specifically for gap filler removal
- Shear filler at bottom and sides of gap
- Five widths, each with three depths
- Sharpened using 120-180 grit abrasive
- Adapt to TSB handles & pneumatic tool

Torlon Adhesive Cutters (TACs)

- TACs designed to remove remnant adhesive and sealant from locations where adhesively bonded nutplates failed
- Diameters to accommodate several nutplate sizes
- Used with drill motor and Andrews Tool Company's Surface Preparation Tool
- Segmented, tetherable mandrels available for drill motor

TACs

Bonded Nutplates During Adhesive Cure

Nutplate

Prototype Evaluation

Andrews Tool & Drill Motor

Additional Material Removal Tools

- Gap Filler Removal (GFR) Bits (with die grinder)
- GFR Discs for narrow gaps and scoring thick elastomeric coatings (with oscillating tools)
- Reamers to remove material from fastener holes

Reamers

Gap Filler Removal (GFR) Discs

GFR Bits

Tool Evaluations

- TSBs, TGBs, GFR Bits and GFR Discs were extensively tested on coated and uncoated composite substrates and found not to damage composites when used properly (minor coating damage observed)
- Material removal evaluations conducted in laboratory and in operational environment showed significant decrease in removal times versus other nonmetallic tools (up to 3X depending on application)

25° Angle

45° Angle

TSB-1200 @ 25° Tool Angle on Primed Test Panel

Sectioned to Assess Porosity

≈ 270 kg Load

Uncoated Test Panel (for TGBs & GFR Bits)

Test Panel Gap Side Walls

Test Panel Gap Bottom (arrows show Torlon on surface)

Transition and Commercialization

Torlon Tools & Accessories

TGB Pneumatic Kit

- Needed accessories were developed or identified
- Removal procedures using Torlon tools were drafted
- Close cooperation with U.S. Air Force maintainers during development drove many tool and accessory features and greatly aided transition and implementation
- Commercialized under EnduroSharp® brand name

Segmented, Tetherable Mandrel for TACs

AFRL TAC Kit